

Capacity Building and Job Performance among Junior Officers of the Nigeria Air Force

Charles Akpo OWOH

&

Tunde OSENI

Department of Politics and International Relations, Lead City University, Ibadan

Abstract

The capacity and performance of a workforce drives their level of productivity in that organization because the staff or personnel make it possible to achieve organizational objectives. Research have it that, despite the bilateral and multilateral support that have been provided to the Armed Forces, most especially the NAF, Nigeria has failed to put the country in her right position in terms of peace and security. The failure to meet up with the expectations of political representatives and Nigerian citizens has led to several questions on the level of education and performance of troops. This research investigates the need for capacity building exercise as a means to boost job performance amongst junior officers of Nigerian Air Force (NAF). This research adopted survey research design while questionnaire served as the research instrument. The study sampled the entire 1320 junior staff of the NAF. However, only 1,200 copies of the distributed questionnaire were valid and analysed with SPSS v23. The results of this study shows that officers at the Nigerian Air Force are aware of several capacity building programmes, however, only of this training opportunities are available to the junior offers. Also, majority of the officers are at least satisfied with the few trainings they had. Similarly, the officers revealed lack of trainings breed low level of job performance. The study, therefore, concludes that rigorous adoption of the proposed techniques will help the Nigerian Air Force increase capability. In the Nigerian Air Force (NAF), efficient and productive human resource management is fundamental to increased performance. In recommendation, the Nigerian Air Force (NAF), for its part, may use capacity building to ensure strict adherence to its human resource regulations. This in return will also boost their morale and yield improved job performance.

Keywords: Capacity Building, Job Performance, Nigeria Air Force

Introduction

The remarkable development of the twenty-first century is the consequence of a new view on the value of investing in individuals or staff and organizational human resources, as well as the new capacity of capacity strategies in numerous fields in organizations and societies. Humans, institutions, and communities have the capacity to perform well, to identify and achieve their goals, and to adjust when necessary for sustainability, progress, and advancement. Capacity development is considered an endogenous dynamic process that relies on one's motivation, effort, and perseverance to learn and progress which enables organizations to change, flourish and grow. Some of the major capacities that enhance growth include leadership development and knowledge networking (Mouallem & Analoui, 2018). Capacity is the engine that drives performance in every organization and makes it possible for

an organization to meet its goals and achieve its overall mission (Farazmand, 2017). Understanding capacity is critical because shift within an organization occurs. Meanwhile, capacity building and job performance of employees are indispensable components of human resource management. It's a means of reducing uncertainty in the marketplace and achieving organisational goals (Cawthra and Robin, 2018). Essentially, capacity building and job performance of employees provide sustainable opportunities in accordance with employees' aspirations and talents for acquiring knowledge to accelerate economic and social benefits of themselves and their workplace.

Capacity building programmes have been adjudged to be a critical factor in Nigerian security sector, culminating in their positions as major determinants of officers' professional advancement (Chukwuma, 2008). Officers' participation in capacity building training transform role performance abilities and skill-sets of officers in such a way and manner that they meet and fit adequately into the challenges of their job functions.

Also, the US military has, over the last decade, supported Nigeria Armed Forces in building an institutional capacity in order to tackle the security challenges the Continent. This was carried out through a various capacity building programmes and partnerships. Meanwhile, the Nigerian Air force faces a wide range of operational challenges, including arms and drugs smuggling, human trafficking, banditry and oil theft, militancy, and terrorism. Nigeria has always desired for a quality armed forces especially for its air power delivery.

Each force units in the Nigerian armed forces now progressively offer professional education and training of its manpower in form of capacity building to equip its teaming workforce and combatants in theatres develop the requisite skills and expand the career roles of its collaborative workforce. This is expected to generate enthusiasm, new skill-sets and approach to securitization affair for officers of the armed forces. The Nigerian Air Force (NAF) is not an exception to the training in form of capacity building, of her personnel, that is, the junior officers for its operational efficiency. Since, the air and ground crew are also deep-seated in the frontline operations which is the first point of contact in the employment of airpower. For instance, in December 2021, an Adjutant Major General of the California National Guard (CNG) in the United State, Major General David Baldwin expressed the readiness of his organization to partner the Nigerian Air Force (NAF) in the development of its Air-Ground Integration School and improving its safety plans and strategies on intelligence-gathering, cyber warfare sequencing in NAF operations (Martha, 2021).

This has mostly been flawed by many security strategists and analysts since most of the projected engagements on capacity building would only support the non-commissioned senior officers. Meanwhile, junior officers constitute mostly 70% of workforce in NAF operations. This also expedites how NAF recently reviewed its training curriculum in the Air Force Institute of Technology (AFIT) for its personnel to meet emerging domestic and international security challenges. Similarly, the Nigerian Air Force Regiment (NAF Regiment), with its capability for force protection and projection of NAF airfield and infrastructure, will be better positioned in combating insurgents and bandits exploits in the country.

Statement of the Problem

The recent threats to internal security have manifested in different ways and the enhancement of capacity building among the rank and files have suddenly become the new normal, particularly among the senior officers to control and contain security threats during combats theatre in the face of the surging domestic security pitfalls, although the Nigerian Air-force have been recently adjudged to perform complementary functions in a bid to scale-up internal security (Duke, 2019). Particularly, studies on evaluation of the security sector management of capacity building and job performance structure among junior officers of the Nigerian air-force are still scare.

Furthermore, while there is a consensus that capacity building is key to promoting job performance in an institution or organization (Nwankwo & Okorie, 2015; Okoh, & Onoriode, 2019), more attention needs to be drawn to the way to go about it, particularly in the Nigerian Air Force. While the existing works on the identified challenge charged by this study are scanty, the methodology deployed to capture the cognitive assessment and Flight Lieutenant, Flying Officer, Pilot Officer, Corporal, Lance Corporal, Aircraftmen and women's job performance of the Nigerian Air- Army in its operations. This study investigates whether the junior officers in the rank and files are being enlisted in the capacity building plan of the Nigerian Air-force. Can the system of Air Force (NAF) recruitment help with capacity building?

Research Questions

The objective of this study is to assess the management of capacity building and job performance structure among the junior officers of the Nigeria Air Force. In order to achieve the above objective of this study, the following research question are formulated, the following questions are formulated:

- 1 What is the training awareness level of capacity building among the junior officers of the Nigerian Air Force?
- 2 What is the perception of the capacity building among the junior officers of the Nigerian Air Force?
- 3 To what extent has the capacity building influence work performance among the junior officers of the Nigerian Air Force?

Conceptual Review

Examining Extant Debates on Capacity Building

Capacity building is the strengthening of skills, competencies and abilities of people in order at which they are able to effectively work towards the achievement of organizational goals and objectives. Specifically, capacity building encompasses scientific, technological, organizational, institutional and resource capabilities (Duke, 2019). It was also conceived as a theoretical approach to social or personal development that deals with knowing and working towards the realization of the organizational goals and objectives through the training, exposure and enlightenment of personnel to enhance their abilities which will enable them to achieve sustainable result. The Danish Ministry of Defence (2016) defines

capacity building as an important task for the defence sector which includes advice, training, education, and mentoring within the security sector. Its overall objective is to prevent conflict from evolving by enabling, receiving nations to take care of their own security. UNDP (2003) and Nwankwo & Okorie (2015) defined capacity building to cover human resources development and the strengthening of managerial systems, institutional development that involves community participation and creation of an enabling environment.

Similarly, Barrett, et al. (2013) define capacity building as a process for strengthening the management and governance of an organization so that it can effectively achieve its objectives and fulfill its mission. Also, Beesley & Shebby (2010) and adopted by the Grantmakers for Effective Organizations (2003) developed a definition of effectiveness that grantees and federal, state, or local governments have adopted as a definition of capacity. This, however, added a depth to the definition by broadening what is meant by capacity building. The ability of an organization to fulfill its mission through a blend of sound management, strong governance, and a persistent rededication to achieving results. By merging the straightforward definition of capacity building with the GEO definition of effectiveness, a more comprehensive definition of capacity building, which will be useful to technical assistance providers, emerges: Capacity building was conceived as an intervention that strengthens an organization's ability to fulfill its mission by promoting sound management, strong governance, and persistent rededication to achieving results. Meanwhile, to Agunyai (2015), capacity building is the planned programs that will impart skills acquired into productive uses to solve wide range of individual and national problems, in this case, national security challenges.

Capacity building is a process or procedure through which the skills, talent and knowledge of an employee is enhanced and increased. In other words, a successful training programme must contribute to the growth and development of the competencies and activation of employees at all levels (Obisi, 1996). Capacity building affects attitude formation in a way that the employees' attitude is shaped with a view to getting their support and partnership in the enterprise. A staff trained appreciates the fact that the organization values his contribution to the sustenance of the enterprise. He feels proud and he is committed to the goals of the organization. French and Seward (1980) suggested in their own view that it's the systematic development and improvement of an industrial ability to perform specific task or job. In consonance to his postulation, Hinrichs (1976) sees it as organisational and individual development can merge, where personal and corporate growth can occur simultaneously. However, he stated further that effective training programmes must demonstrably contribute to the satisfaction of both the trainee's personal goals as well as the organizations goals.

Duke (2019) further believes that no matter how, capacity building is anchored on optimum productivity and it depends on the effectiveness of the workforce. For instance, Nwachukwu (1988) puts it that capacity building is an organizational effort aimed at helping an employee to acquire basic skills required for the efficient execution of functions he was employed for. He explained that employees' productivity is a function of ability, will and determination. In his own assertion, synthesizing all the definitions above, capacity building was presumed purpose of training which is to

achieve a change in the behaviour of the trainee. Also, to Bite and Ramsey, they equally sees it as a programme designed to provide the knowledge, attitude or job skills that would help employees perform their present jobs. Having thoroughly examined extant works, there are purposes for which they have been done. For instance, Shields (2007) explained that each of the systemic factors that may be subject to performance management interventions may be extended to include collective and, in turn, organization-wide dimensions, where managers take active steps to align people with processes and forming a technical system from which to deliver, desired levels of service delivery in cost effective ways. Aligning this to his view, capacity building mission means that an organization has: (a) sufficient numbers of staff who possess the necessary knowledge and skills, (b) appropriate and adequate technical and management systems, (c) suitable physical infrastructure, and (d) ample financial and other resources. Thus, capacity building is not limited to training personnel or the provision of technical assistance, but may include overhauling systems, remodeling physical infrastructure, recruiting new personnel, and improving the efficiency of the use of existing resources (Fixsen, et al, 2012).

Thus, while the existing works on the identified challenge charged by this study are scanty and the faulty methodology deployed to capture the evaluation of military professional education among senior staff of the Armed forces have been overly researched, this study extends the frontiers of the existing views but deviate by focusing on the management of Nigerian Air force education and their job performance structure among junior officers. Thus, from the reviewed literature, it is clear to say that capacity building for employees leads to improvements in the ability of all employees to perform appropriate tasks within the broader set of performance standards of the organization. Studies have indicated that capacity building has a positive influence on employee. Each of the above research works reviewed offered an important contribution to knowledge on capacity building and productivity in the various organs of the Nigerian Air Force (NAF). However, none of these works investigated capacity building especially among the junior officers of the institution. It is this gap, therefore, that this study attempts to bridge.

Armed Forces Education System in Nigeria: Pressing Security Needs from NAF

Officer education occurs in institutional settings, in operational assignments, and through self-development. Institutional training represents the resident training an officer receives either in military or civilian institutions. Self-development encompasses nonresident schooling including individual study, distributive learning, re-search, professional reading, practice, and self-assessment. The strategic objective of the Officer Education System is to provide an education and training system operationally relevant to the current environment, but structured to support the future environment by producing more capable, adaptable, and confident leaders through continuous investment in personal growth and professional development throughout their careers (Ekpa & Tamunomiebi, 2021). To achieve this objective, the NAF has embraced an experiential and competency-based education and training model in its education system. This system integrates current technological capabilities to

rapidly advance learning in both individual and collective training requirements while providing NAF officer the right training and education in the right medium, at the right time and place for success in their next assignment. This medium of supports the NAF service culture and warrior ethos, and produces leaders who can resolve dilemmas under stress, make decisions, and lead formations. The institutional side of the Army is a series of leadership laboratories focused on learning, growing, achieving competency, and getting better training into units.

The goal of the Officer Education System is to produce a corps of leaders who are fully competent in technical, tactical, and leadership skills, knowledge, and experience; understand how the NAF runs; are prepared to operate in a unified action environment; can demonstrate confidence, integrity, critical judgment, and responsibility; operate in an environment of complexity, ambiguity, and rapid change; build effective teams amid organizational and technological change; and adapt to and solve problems creatively. The products of this system are officers who are highly specialized experts, trainers, and leaders; fully competent in technical, tactical, and leadership skills; creative problem solvers, able to function in highly complex and dynamic environments; and proficient operators, maintainers, administrators, and managers of NAF equipment, support activities, and technical systems. Officer leader development is a continuous process that begins with pre-commissioning or pre-appointment training and education (Jalili & Annen, 2019).

The Officer Education System is a sequence of the professional military education for professionals in subjects that enhance knowledge of the science and art of war in air-space. The PME is a progressive education system that prepares leaders for increased responsibilities and successful performance at the next higher level by developing the key knowledge, skills, and attributes they require to operate successfully at that level in any environment. Professional military education is linked to promotions, future assignments, and career management pathways for all officers (Idris, 2019). Currently, officers enter active duty with diverse educational backgrounds and civilian experience. This diversity is amplified by the great variety of service experiences among officers with different branches. The current Officer Education System permits officers to build upon achievements and experience and progress to a higher level of learning and opportunities exist for resident and nonresident instruction. There are multiple paths to obtaining a professional education. However, officers may follow different paths to achieve this.

Methodology

To carry out a systematic assessment of education in the rank and files and its attendant impacts on officers' performance, particularly in NAF. The population of the study comprises of 1,320 junior officers of the Nigerian Air Force (NAF), which accounts for 70% of the total workforce. In an attempt to achieve the stated objectives of this research study, the researcher adopted a purposive sampling technique by involving the entire 1,320 junior officers at the Nigerian Air Force. This sampling technique was adopted because it's a type of sampling in which researchers use their own discretion in selecting individuals of the public to participate in surveys. Questionnaire was the primary source of

data collected and this formed the main instrument of the research questions which were designed in a simple language for the respondents to answer. The questions were presented in a simple and precise structure in open and closed ended format with alternative answers for respondents to explain appropriately. The data were analysed using simple percentage combined with numerical, frequencies, histograms, and percentages. This is to communicate the information effectively. The data collected from members of staffs of the Nigerian Air Force was analysed with Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) v23.

Analysis and Data Presentation

A total of 1,320 copies of the questionnaires were distributed based on the relative strength of the number of the staff at the Nigerian Air Force. However, out of the 1,320 questionnaires that were administered, a total 1,270 was returned and only 1,200 were properly filled and valid. Therefore, a total of 1,200 copies of questionnaires were analysed in this study.

Table 1: Demographic Data Presentation

N	Variables	Frequency	Percentage (%)	
1.	Age	20-29	121	10.1
		30-39	421	35.1
		40-49	388	32.3
		50-59	177	14.8
		60-65	93	7.7
		Total	1200	100
2.	Highest Education Qualification	NCE/ND	231	19.3
		HND/BSc	749	62.4
		MSc/MBA	151	12.6
		PhD	69	5.8
		Total	1200	100
3.	Marital Status	Single	126	10.5
		Married	983	81.9
		Divorced	91	7.6
		Total	1200	100
4.	Categories of Officers	Senior Officer	139	11.6
		Middle Officer	304	25.3
		Junior Officer	757	63.1
		Total	1200	100
5.	Years in Service	5years	589	49.1
		6 to 10years	320	26.7
		11 to 15years	154	12.8
		16 or more	137	11.4
		Total	1200	100

Source: Fieldwork, 2022

The age distribution of the respondent is presented in Table 1. It showed that the highest proportion of the respondents in the study were within the active age (30-39years) with an average mean age of 35.1years. This means that majority (35.1%) of the respondents fall within the ages of 30-39 years. This implication of this is that, the respondents were physically active and they were young.

The level of education of the respondents showed that 62.4% of the respondents (majority) had HND/BSc, 19.3% of the respondents had NCE/ND, 12.6% of the respondents had Master's degree and 5.8% are doctoral degree holders. However, it must be made clear that those who had MSc degree must have completed their bachelor's degree in relevant courses or subject. The implication is that the respondents in the study area are literates.

The marital status of the sampled respondents, presented in the table, revealed that 983 respondents (81.9%) were married, 126 of the respondents (10.5%) were single, while 91 respondents given as 7.6% were divorced. The distribution of respondents by categories of officers showed that most (63.1%) representing 757 of the respondents are junior officer which constitute the major focus of this research. Also, 25.3% representing 304 respondents of the respondents are middle officer while 11.6% representing 139 of the respondents are senior officers.

The distribution of respondents by years in service showed that most (49.1%) of the respondents have been at the institution for at least five years. Also, 26.1% representing 320 of the respondents have been with the Nigerian Air Force (NAF) for up to 10 years. 154 representing 12.8% of the respondents have been with the institution for up to 15 years while 11.4% representing 137 respondents have been with the Nigerian Air Force (NAF) for more than 16 years. The implication is that majority of those who participated in the research study are experienced workers.

RQ1: What is the training awareness level of capacity building among the junior officers of the Nigerian Air Force?

Table 2: Respondents' Awareness of Capacity Building Programs

Awareness level	Frequency	Percentage
Extremely aware	730	60.8
Slightly aware	291	24.3
Not aware	179	14.9
Total	1200	100

Source: Fieldwork, 2022

The distribution of respondents as shown in Table 2 presented answers to the question of whether members of the Nigerian Air Force (NAF) are aware of any capacity building programs. The result disclosed that 60.8% representing 730 respondents are extremely aware, 24.3% representing 291 respondents are slightly aware, while 14.9% are not aware of any capacity building program in the military institution. This result shows that majority of the respondents agree that they are aware of any

capacity building program in the Nigerian Air Force (NAF). Most of the respondents emphasized that, the only capacity building that they had was the 'pre-training' program they had at the entry of the institution.

RQ2: What is the perception of the capacity building among the junior officers of the Nigerian Air Force?

Table 3: Respondents Degree of Capacity Building

Items	Frequency	Percentage
High	251	20.9
Moderate	245	20.4
Fair	221	18.4
Low	360	30.0
Not Decided	123	10.3
Total	1200	100

Source: Fieldwork, 2022

The distribution of respondents on the degree of capacity building in the Nigeria Air Force (NAF) was shown in Table 3. The result revealed that, 30.0% of the respondents said the rate or degree of capacity building in NAF was low, 20.9% of the respondents said the capacity building in NAF was high, 20.4% of the respondent said moderate, 18.4% of the respondents said it was fair, and 10.3% of the respondents were unable to decide. The implication of this is that, majority of the respondent (30.0%) representing 360 respondents, believe that their capacity building experience with the Nigerian Air Force (NAF) is low. During personal discussion, majority of the respondents confessed that most junior officers do not have access to training and other capacity building initiatives when compared with their senior colleagues.

Table 4: Respondents' Level of Satisfaction with the Capacity Building Programs

Items	Frequency	Percentage
Satisfied	716	59.7
Dissatisfied	284	23.7
Unsure	200	16.7
Total	1200	100

Source: Fieldwork, 2022

The distribution of respondents was presented in Table 4. The table answered the question of whether the junior officers are satisfied with the training programs in the Nigerian Air Force (NAF). The result showed that 59.7% of the respondents are satisfied, 23.7% of the respondents are dissatisfied, while 16.7% said were neutral in their responses. The implication of this is that, majority of the respondents are said to be satisfied with the training they had. In further discussion with the respondents, many of them clarified that the training they are satisfied with is the "Pre-training" exercise done after their names have been shortlisted by the institution. However, they also believe that they would have been

more effective and productive if additional trainings were done or conducted for them. Most of the junior workers revealed that they do not have access to trainings except the “pre-training” exercise being done for them.

RQ3: To what extent has the capacity building influence work performance among the junior officers of the Nigerian Air Force?

Table 5: Capacity Building and Job Performance of NAF Junior Officers

Items	Frequency	Percentage
Improved Operation	321	26.8
High Morale	175	14.6
Low Morale	587	48.9
I don't Know	117	9.8
Total	1200	100

Source: Fieldwork, 2022

The distribution of respondents is presented in Table 5. It revealed that 26.8% of the respondent are of the opinion that lack of capacity building programs improves job operations, 14.6% of the respondents are of the opinion that it increases the morale of the officers. However, 48.9% of the respondents believed that lack of capacity building in the Nigerian Air Force (NAF) breeds low morale and productivity, while 9.8% of the respondents said they are oblivious of the influence of capacity building on their job performance. The implication of this is that, majority of the junior officer of the force believe that lack of, or access to capacity building programs such as training and so on have an impact of the officers. In an interactive session with the respondents, most of these junior officers believe that it is when the institution organises capacity building programs that they can individually improve and learn more skill that will help their operation and functioning.

Discussion of Findings

The purpose of this study is to assess the management of capacity building and job performance structure among the junior officers of the Nigeria Air Force. From the demographic data of the respondents, the data received indicates that the highest proportion of the respondents in the study were within the active age (30-39years). This implies that the respondents were physically active and they were young. The level of education of the respondents presented showed that most (62.4%) of the respondents had HND/BSc, while 12.6% of the respondents had Master's degree and 5.8% are doctoral degree holders. However, it must be made clear that those who have MSc and PhD must have completed their bachelor's degree in relevant courses or subjects. The shows that the respondents are literate. The distribution of respondents by years in service revealed that most (49.1%) of the respondents have been at the institution for at least five years. This indicates that the majority of those who participated in the research study are experienced officers.

Research question one of this study was formulated to find out the awareness level of capacity building among the junior officers of the Nigerian Air Force. The result shows that majority of the respondents are aware of any capacity building program in the Nigerian Air Force (NAF). Most of the respondents emphasized that, the only capacity building they had was the 'pre-training' program during their admission into the institution. The results of this study correlate with those of a researcher who states that, the key goals of capacity building or training for new recruits are to provide new employees with the essential knowledge and abilities to achieve the company's or organization's intended goal. The objective of training an employee, according to the author, is for the employee to be better prepared and adapt to changes in the nature of his work and to broaden the trainee's understanding of the society/organization in which he or she lives and positively develop frame of mind, and to provide employees the flexibility to adjust their work schedules while still performing at a high level (Hamadamin & Atan, 2019; Sabuhari, et al., 2020).

Research question two inquires about the perception of the capacity building among the junior officers of the Nigerian Air Force. The responses gathered showed that the respondents' capacity building experience with the Nigerian Air Force (NAF) is low. During personal discussion, majority of the respondents disclosed that, even though there are opportunities, most junior officers do not have access to training and other capacity building initiatives as their senior colleagues. However, the junior staff happened to be satisfied with the number of trainings they had.

Research question three was to determine the extent to which capacity building influence work performance among the junior officers of the Nigerian Air Force. The result of the enquiry shows that lack of capacity building in the Nigerian Air Force (NAF) breeds low morale and productivity. The implication of this is that, majority of the junior officers of the force believe that lack of, or access to capacity building programs such as training, among others, have an impact on the officers. In an interactive session with the respondents, most of these junior officers believe that it is when the institution organises capacity building programs that they could individually improve and learn more skills that would help their operations and functioning. The findings of this research correlate with the research of Ismail, et al (2021) who posit that there exists a relationship between increasing human resource capacity and improving employee job performance.

The NAF Manual of Training and Career Progression document AFP 248, are the guidelines for training in the Nigerian Air Force. The documents stipulate that there are three levels of trainings for officers which are, the fundamental, intermediate as well as advanced for the different staffs of Air Forces Specialties (AFS), especially the aircrew. This remains in enhancement to Professional Military Education (PME), junior and senior command and team training courses as well as the defence management programs at National Institute of Policy and Strategic Studies or the National Defence College (NDC).

Conclusion and Recommendations

The central focus of the research is to assess the capacity building and job performance among junior officers of the Nigeria Air Force (NAF) in order to provide methods to solve the Service's HRM and capacity-building concerns. This paper recognized that capacity building initiatives or programs is a

significant technique for improving human resource management in the Nigerian Air Force (NAF). The study discovered that documents such as the Professional Military Education (PME) and the Training Needs Analysis (TNA), the NAF manual of training and career progression, AFP 248, and other relevant documents attempted to develop and enhance its officers for increased performance. Inadequate implementation of human resource policy, insufficient financing, insufficient training, as well as a lack of feedback mechanisms are among the difficulties to capacity building noted in this study. It is also imperative to note that, the methods were intended to improve the chances of junior officers in the Nigerian Air Force developing their capacity.

The results of this study shows that officers at the Nigerian Air Force are aware of several capacity building programmes, however, only few of these training opportunities are available to the junior offers. Also, majority of the officers are at least satisfied with the few trainings they had. Similarly, the officers revealed lack of trainings breed low level of job performance. The study, therefore, concludes that rigorous adoption of the proposed techniques will help the Nigerian Air Force increase capability. In the Nigerian Air Force (NAF), efficient and productive human resource management is fundamental to increased performance.

In recommendation, the federal government should ensure that the NAF receives a good percentage of its annual allocation (if not all) to support its numerous junior officer capacity building initiatives. The Nigerian Air Force (NAF), for its part, may use capacity building to ensure strict adherence to its human resource regulations. This, in return, will also boost their morale and yield improved job performance. Also, improved employee training, increased employee understanding of the company's human resource policy, and the establishment of a feedback system for assessing and monitoring officers should all be implemented as soon as possible.

References

- Agunyai, S. C. (2015). Manpower development, capacity building and service delivery in Ife-East Local Government Area, Osun State, Nigeria. *Journal of Public Administration and Policy Research*, 7(1), 1-14.
- Amuno, J. (2019). The effect of training on the on-the-job performance of graduates of the centre for Management Development in Nigeria. Unpublished Ph.D Thesis, University of Ibadan.
- Anyakoha, C. (2019). *Job analysis as a tool for improved organizational performance of SMEs in Lagos, Nigeria*. *Central European Journal of Labour Law and Personnel Management*, 2(1), 7-16.
- Banjoko, S. (1996), *Human Resources Management: An Expository Approach*. Lagos, Saban Publishers.
- Barrett, S., Kincaid, D. March, A. (2013). *Building Coaching Capacity*. Presented at the 2013 PBIS Leadership Forum.
- Beesley, A. D. & Shebby, S. (2010). *Evaluating capacity building in education: The North Central*

- Comprehensive Center. Paper presented at the Annual meeting of the American Educational Research Association, Denver, Colorado, May 2010.
- Cawthra, G. & Robin L. (2018). *Governing Insecurity: Democratic Control of Military and Security Establishments in Transitional Democracies*. London: ZED Books, 2018, Pg 12-31
- Danish Ministry of Defence (October 24, 2016). *Defence capacity building*. Retrieved from <http://www.fmn.dk/eng/allabout/pages/capacitybuilding.aspx/>
- Duke, O. O. (2019). Capacity Building of the Nigerian Armed Forces and Security Challenges. *International Journal of Trend in Scientific Research and Development*. 4(1), 456-470.
- Ekpa, I. H. & Tamunomiebi, M. D. (2021). Education and Organizational Performance of the Nigeria Arm Forces. *RSU Journal of Strategic and Internet Business*, 6(3), 2150-2165.
- Ekwealor, C. T. & Faluyi, O. T (2020). Security institutions and democratic governance in Nigeria. In *Democratic Practice and Governance in Nigeria*, 190-206, Routledge.
- Emmanuel, E. Y. (2014). The Link between Human Resource Capacity Building and Job Performance, *International Journal of Human Resource Studies*, Vol. 4, 3, 139-146.
- Farazmand, A. (2017). Innovation in Strategic Human Resource Management: Building Capacity in the Age of Globalization. *Public Organization Review* 4, Pg 3–24.
- Field Manual (2016) 6-22, *Army Leadership: Competent, Confident, and Agile*.
- Fixsen, D. L., Blase, K. A., Duda, M. A., & Horner, R. (2012). *Assessment of State Capacity for Scaling up Evidence-Based Practices*. *State Capacity Assessment (SCA)* University of North Carolina Chapel Hill.
- Grantmakers for Effective Organizations. (2003). *Grantmakers for effective organizations: Theory of change*. Prepared by Steven La France and Rick Green.
- Hamadamin, H. H. & Atan, T. (2019). *The impact of strategic human resource management practices on competitive advantage sustainability: The mediation of human capital development and employee commitment*. *Sustainability*, 11(20), 57-82.
- Hicks, G.A. & Moon Gullet, R.C. (1976). *Organization Theory and Behaviour*, Tokyo Mcgraw Hill, Kogakusha.
- Idris, M. I. (2019). Professional military education for the modern officer: the Nigerian experience. In D. Jalili, and H. Annen (Eds.), *Professional military education: a cross cultural survey*, 35-42.
- Ismail, A. A., Majid, A. H., Jibrin-Bida, M. & Joarder, M. H. (2021). *Moderating effect of management support on the relationship between HR practices and employee performance in Nigeria*, *Global Business Review*, 22(1), 132-150.
- Jalili, D. & Annen, H. (2019). Professional military education: A cross-cultural survey. *Studies in Military Psychology and Pedagogy*. Switzerland: Peter Lang. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.3726/b15676>
- Martha O. (2021). Capacity Building: US, Nigerian Air Force to Develop Integration School, available

at, <https://von.gov.ng/2021/12/08/capacity-building-us-nigerian-air-force-to-develop-integration-school/>

Martha, O. (2021). *Capacity Building: US, Nigerian Air Force to Develop Integration School*. Retrieved from: <https://von.gov.ng/2021/12/08/capacity-building-us-nigerian-airforce-to-develop-integration-school/>

Mouallem, L. & Analoui, F. (2018). The Need For Capacity Building In Human Resource Management Related Issues: A Case Study From The Middle East. Lebanon.

Nwachukwu, C. C. (1988). *Management Theory and Practice* – Africana Publishing, Onitsha.

Nwankwo, C. & Okorie, E. N. (2015). Human capacity building and sustainable development in the 21st century: Implications and challenges in Nigeria. *Journal of Business and Management*. 17(7), 17-24.

Okoh, L. & Onoriode, H. (2019) The Need for Capacity Building in Human Resources Management Development in the Financial Institutions in Nigeria, *International Journal of Innovative Finance and Economics Research* 7(2), 76-81.

Sabuhari, R., Sudiro, A., Irawanto, D. & Rahayu, M. (2020). *The effects of human resource flexibility, employee competency, organizational culture adaptation and job satisfaction on employee performance*. *Management Science Letters*, 10(8), 1775-1786.

Shields, J. (2007). *Managing Employee Performance and Reward: Concepts, Practices, Strategies*. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press.